

1 **Epidemiology of the injuries sustained by elite Spanish under-18 and under-20 rugby players**

2 **Abstract**

3 This study examine the injuries suffered by players (n=166) of the Spanish national men's under-18 and
4 under-20 rugby teams between 2015 and 2017, and identifies the actions involved in their appearance.
5 All injuries (total n=78) sustained during matches and training were recorded as recommended by World
6 Rugby, and injury incidence rates per 1000 player-hours (ph) calculated for both types of activity.
7 Injuries occurred more commonly during matches than during training (incidence 105.3 [95%CI 78.7-
8 131.9] per 1000 [ph] of match play, vs. 1.16 [95%CI 0.69-1.62] per 1000 ph of training), and most days
9 absent per 1000 ph during matches with <3 days rest since the previous match (4209.2 [95%CI 3516.2-
10 4902.1] per 1000 ph of match play, vs. 1947.4 [95%CI 1511.8-2382.9] per 1000 ph of match play in
11 matches with >3 days rest). These results provide information that may be useful in the development
12 of strategies aimed at reducing the incidence of injuries.

13 **Keywords:** epidemiology, youth players, rugby, injury

14

15 **Introduction**

16 Injuries sustained during adolescence can have short and long-term health consequences, and can
17 certainly be one of the reasons why sportspersons reduce their physical activity or change sports [1].
18 They can also have social and economic consequences for players and affect the sporting success of
19 their clubs [2]. Epidemiological studies can provide information useful for the development of strategies
20 aimed at reducing the incidence of injuries [3, 4]. Studies undertaken in the field of professional rugby
21 have reported a high incidence of injuries, ranging from 66.0 to 96.3 per 1000 player-hours (ph) of
22 match play [5]. The incidence of injury among younger players is less clear. Some studies suggest that
23 the incidence of injury among those attending rugby academies is lower than among professional players
24 [6, 7]. Another reports that the incidence of injuries in the Spanish under-18 team during its involvement
25 in four European competitions was higher than among non-national team players of similar age [8]. Yet
26 another reports the incidence of injuries among players in the Spanish national under-20 team to be no

27 different to that seen among players at clubs and academies [9]. For a clearer picture to emerge - and for
28 strategies to be developed that might help prevent injuries - studies are need to closely monitor the
29 frequency of injuries sustained by players of different ages. In Spain, where young people make up some
30 30% of all federated rugby players, such information is of particular importance. The aim of the present
31 work was, therefore, to examine the incidence of injuries among members of the the Spanish men's
32 under-18 and under-20 national teams, and the actions involved in their appearance.

33

34 **Methods**

35 This longitudinal, prospective cohort study was designed to provide Level 2b evidence[10]. The injuries
36 sustained by the players of the Spanish men's under-18 and under-20 national teams during the 2015-
37 2016 and 2016-2017 seasons were recorded. All injured players were monitored until recovery by
38 national team physician through contact with player, club physicians and health insurance. The study
39 received approval by the Review Board of the Universidad Camilo José Cela, Madrid, Spain. All players
40 involved , and their parents/guardians if required, provided informed consent to be included in the study.

41 The total number of players monitored was 166, 76 in the 2015-2016 season (under-18 n=34, under-20
42 n=42), and 90 in the 2016-2017 season (under-18 n=32, under-20 n=58). All were healthy at the start of
43 each season. The mean age (years), height (cm), body weight (kg) for the study period was recorded
44 for both teams. The position played by all players was noted. The activities of the under-18 team during
45 these seasons consisted of preparing for and participating in European tournaments within the
46 appropriate category; those of the under-20 team consisted of preparing for and participating in
47 European tournaments in its category, and the corresponding Trophy tournament. The under-18 team
48 played 6 European tournament matches and 5 preparation friendlies (total n=11), and the under-20 team
49 played 6 European tournament matches, 4 Trophy tournament matches, and 6 friendlies (total n=16).
50 Among these overall 27 matches, 10 were played with <3 days rest since the previous match, and 17
51 were played with ≥ 3 days rest.

52 All injuries suffered were recorded by the national team physician- both in training and during matches
53 - as were the actions involved in their appearance. Injuries were recorded following the World Rugby
54 protocol developed by Fuller et al. [11]. A primary injury was defined as any physical complaint
55 sustained by a player that prevented the player from training fully or playing in a match for >24 h. A
56 recurrent injury was defined as any injury of the same type and in the same place as a primary injury,
57 following recovery from that primary injury. Injury severity was recorded as the number of days that
58 elapsed between sustaining the injury and returning to full physical condition (training- and match-
59 ready) on the following scale: slight injury 2-3 days, mild injury 4-7 days, moderate injury 8-28 days,
60 and severe injury >28 days. The date of injury was recorded, as was the date on which the affected
61 player returned to normal training/match activity, whether protection was worn, the position of the
62 injured player, the location of the injury, the type of injury (following the Orchard injury code) [12],
63 whether it was a contact injury, whether it was a recurrent injury, whether it was sustained during
64 training or match play, the activity underway at the time of injury, the time the injury was sustained if
65 in a match, whether the injury was due to a foul, whether that foul was deemed dangerous play, the
66 playing surface on which the injury occurred, the diagnostic tests performed, and the treatment
67 prescribed. All data were collected by the national team physician on an Excel spreadsheet (Microsoft
68 Corp., Redmond, WA, USA) adapted according to Fuller et al. [11]. In addition, the number of minutes
69 spent in training by each team over the two years was recorded, as was the number of matches played
70 (it should be noted that the duration of under-18 matches is 70 min instead of the normal 80 min),
71 following the recommendations of the World Rugby Guide [13].

72 Data were described descriptively as frequencies and percentages. Frequencies were compared using
73 the Chi-squared test, and the number of days lost due to injury using the Student t test. For some
74 comparisons, the results of both teams were taken together to improve the statistical power. The
75 incidence of injuries during training and matches was recorded as the number of injuries per 1000 ph,
76 with 95% confidence intervals (95%CI). Injury burden is presented (mean severity X incidence/1000
77 ph= days absent/1000 ph) to show the overall cost of injuries to the team in terms of days absent from a

78 given period of exposure. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$. All analyses were performed using SPSS
79 software v.20.0 (IBM Corp, Armonk, NY, USA).

80

81 **Results**

82 Taking into account the two years of the study, the mean age of the under-18 players was 17.3 ± 0.5 years;
83 their mean weight was 86.6 ± 11.7 kg, and their mean height 181 ± 7 cm. Similarly, the mean age of the
84 under-20 players over the two years of the study was 18.7 ± 0.5 years; their mean weight was 93.2 ± 16.2
85 kg, and their mean height 182 ± 6 cm. A total of 192.5 ph of match play, and 7470 ph of training were
86 monitored for the under-18 team, and 320 ph of match play and 13170 ph of training for the under-20
87 team.

88 A total of 78 injuries were recorded over the two study seasons, with 27 among the under-18 players,
89 and 51 among the under-20 players (Table 1). The overall incidence of injuries sustained during match
90 play was higher than during training (105.3 [95%CI 78.7-131.9] per 1000 ph compared to 1.16 [95%CI
91 0.69-1.62] per 1000 ph) and the injury burden was greater for match (2812.2 [95%CI 2422.9-3201.4]
92 days absence per 1000 ph) than for training (11.5 [95%CI 6.9-16.2] days absence per 1000 ph). The
93 number of injuries sustained during match play was higher for the under-20 team- 35 vs. 19 ($p < 0.05$)
94 for the under-18 team, but no significant differences were observed the incidence of injuries in the under-
95 20 team (109.3 [95%CI] per 1000 ph) compared to (98.7 [95%CI 56.5-140.8]) for the under-18 team
96 or in the injury burden (2931.2 [95% CI 2432.5-3429.9] days absence per 1000 ph vs 2597.8[95% CI
97 1978.3-3217.2] days absence per 1000 ph). Taking the results for both teams together, the incidence of
98 match play injuries was 138.4 (95%CI 89.9-186.9) per 1000 ph when had < 3 days between games
99 compared to 85.0 (95%CI 54.3-115.7) for ≥ 3 days between games and injury burden of match play was
100 higher when < 3 days had elapsed since the previous match (4209.2 [95%CI 3516.2-4902.1] days
101 absence per 1000 ph vs. 1947.4 [95%CI 1511.8-2382.9] days absence per 1000 ph with ≥ 3 days).

102 Taking both teams together, the mean number of days-lost per injury was 21.5 days. The mean days-
103 lost to injuries sustained during a match was 26.6 days compared 9.96 days ($p < 0.05$) for training-induced

104 injuries. A total of 27 (34.6%) injuries were mild, 25 (32.1%) were moderate, 14 (17.9%) were severe,
105 and 12 (15.4%) were slight. The injuries sustained during matches were most commonly moderate (19;
106 35.2%) while those sustained during training were most commonly mild (9; 37.5%) (Table 2).

107 The most common injuries sustained during matches were sprains (35.2%) and concussion 16.7% (Table
108 3 and 4). The injuries most commonly sustained during training were ankle sprains (25.0%). Concussion
109 was the injury with the greatest incidence at 17.5 (95%CI 6.1-28.9) per 1000 ph of match play, while
110 the injury burden was 268.6 (95% CI 230.3-307.0) days absence per 1000 ph. Again, taking both teams
111 together, most injuries were sustained during the third quarter of matches (17; 31.5%), followed by the
112 fourth and second quarters 14 (25.9% for each), and finally the first quarter 9 (16.7%).

113 Of the 54 players injured during matches, 48 (88.9%) used some form of protection (e.g., mouthguard
114 or skullcap); only 6 (11.1%) used no protection.

115 No significant differences were seen between the incidence of injuries sustained by forwards and backs
116 during match play (97.3 [95% IC:63.0-131.5] vs. 103.2 [95% IC:65.6-140.8] per 1000 ph of match play
117 respectively), and no significant differences were seen between the mean number day-lost per injury
118 (20.1 days vs 32.7 days [p=0.2]). No significant differences were seen between these variables with
119 respect to injuries sustained during training (0.88[95% IC:0.45-1.31] vs. 0.66 [95% IC:0.2 -1.12] per
120 1000 ph of training; 9.9 days vs 10.2 days [p=0.9]).

121 Again, taking both teams together, tackling was the action that caused most injuries during matches (33
122 of the total 54 recorded). Of these tackle-induced injuries, 23 (42.6%) were sustained by the player being
123 tackled, and 10 (18.5%) by the tackler. Seven injuries (13%) were sustained during a ruck, 8 (14.8%)
124 during moments of no contact, 3 (5.6%) during a maul, 2 (3.7%) during a scrum, and 1 through a
125 collision (1.9%). All the injuries recorded during matches were thus caused through trauma; not one
126 was caused by overuse. Of the injuries sustained during training, 3 (12.5%) were caused by overuse,
127 and 21 (87.5%) by contact.

128 Of the injuries sustained during matches, 13 (24.1%) were associated with fouls and 5 with dangerous
129 play (9.3%). Forty six injuries were produced on a grass field (85.2%) and 8 (14.8%) on an artificial

130 surface. During training, 18 (75%) injuries were sustained on a grass surface, 4 (16.7%) on an artificial
131 surface, and 2 (8.3%) in the gymnasium. Three (5.6%) match-sustained injuries required surgery.

132

133 **Discussion**

134 This is the first study to examine the incidence of injuries in Spanish sub-18 and sub-20 national rugby
135 team players. It is difficult to compare the present results with those reported for non-elite players of
136 similar age since- the demands placed on such players are simply not the same[14]. However, the present
137 incidence rates for both teams are higher than the corresponding rates recorded for players at academies
138 and under-18 club teams [6, 15] and for other under-20 national teams [9]. In addition, the results for
139 the under-18 team are similar to those recorded for professional rugby players (87.1-96.3 per 1000 ph)[2,
140 5], and slightly higher than those recorded for elite-level rugby schools in England for the corresponding
141 age group 77.0 per 1000 ph [16]. The incidence of injuries for the under-20 team was, however, higher
142 than for the same professional rugby players[2, 5]. The differences in the number of injuries seen
143 between the present under-18 and under-20 teams, at least, might be partly explained by the latter's body
144 greater body mass(larger bodies might translate into collisions involving more energy). Under-20 team
145 players may have a similar body mass to professional players [17]; however, no difference was seen in
146 the incidence of injury or injury burden between the groups.

147 For both teams together, the incidence of injury during training was 1.16 per 1000 ph. This is slightly
148 lower than that reported for English rugby schools and academies (1.4 and 2.1 per 1000 h respectively)
149 [18], but lower than that reported for professional rugby players (3.0 per 1000 h) [19]. In the present
150 study, injuries were more commonly sustained during matches than during training, as reported for
151 players of similar age and professional rugby players [6, 18, 19].

152 The mean number of days-lost per injury was 26.6 compared to 32.0 days reported for other players of
153 similar age [6, 9]. This might be partially explained in that the present elite teams had a physicians
154 available at all times, which might have led to more rapid diagnoses being made and earlier attention
155 being given. Studies have shown an inverse association between the number of injury recurrences and

156 level of play, perhaps due to higher-level teams' better access to medical assessment, more accurate
157 diagnoses and better control of recovery and rehabilitation [20].

158 Taking both present teams together, the most common injury sustained during matches was concussion.
159 Its incidence and injury burden was slightly lower than that reported for elite rugby schools in England
160 (in which under-18 and under-20 players' data were taken together; 20.0 per 1000ph of match time) [16],
161 and the incidence was higher than that reported for other players in the same under-18 to under-20 age
162 range (1.8-6.0 per 1000 ph of match time) [7, 15]. The fact that medical attention was available to the
163 present national teams might help explain the greater recording of concussion for their players compared
164 to non-elite teams of the same age groups, the condition being more readily recognised[21]. An increase
165 in the incidence of concussion has been reported for English professional rugby players since 2011.
166 This might be due to better knowledge of this injury and the availability of better protocols and
167 diagnostic tools, but a true increase cannot be ruled out [22].

168 The third quarter of the game was when most of the present injuries were recorded; the fewest were
169 recorded in the first quarter. The same has been reported by other authors [19]. The greater incidence
170 of injury in the third quarter might be related to insufficient warming up or lost concentration after the
171 half-time rest [23].

172 Importantly, the present work takes into account the rest time between matches (see table 5 for example
173 training camp and tournament structures) and the results show that more injury burden were sustained
174 when <3 days had elapsed between them. This agrees with that reported for professional rugby players
175 [8]. At 48 h after a match, the markers of muscle damage remain at high levels, suggesting players are
176 not completely match-ready at this point and more likely to suffer an injury [24, 25]. Thus, fatigue may
177 play a part in the aetiology of injury [26]. In professional rugby league players it has been shown that
178 good tackling technique diminishes with fatigue [27], which might increase the likelihood of associated
179 injury.

180 All the present in-match injuries were caused by contact, with tackling the action most usually involved.
181 This is similar to that reported for players of similar age, and for adult professionals, with the player

182 being tackled the one most commonly hurt [6, 19, 28-30]. However, some authors suggest that this is
183 simply a reflection of the number of tackles that occur in a game compared to other types of action [31].
184 World Rugby changed the legal height of tackles in an attempt to reduce the risk injury, but the did not
185 change [32]. The risk involved in tackling might, however, be lowered by improving player technique;
186 it has at least been observed that professional players who injured in the tackle have a poor
187 technique[33].

188 No differences were seen in the incidence of injuries sustained during match play and in days-lost
189 between forwards and backs. Previous studies have not reported difference incidence values for player
190 positions[22]; simply comparing injury numbers between studies is of little use since the time periods
191 involved are rarely the same. It is also difficult to compare the incidence of injuries sustained on the
192 different surfaces taken into account in the present study given the small numbers involved.

193 During training, contact was the most common cause of injury; overuse injuries were few, a result quite
194 different to that reported in a prior study on the Spanish under-18 team covering four European
195 tournaments [8]. This discrepancy might be explained by differences in the amount of training, and even
196 the use of the right footwear for the different surfaces involved [34]. Other work that examined injuries
197 to players attending rugby schools and academies does not mention whether contact was the cause [18].

198

199 **Conclusions**

200 Injuries appear to be more commonly sustained when there are <3 days of rest between matches. It
201 would seem wise, therefore, to ensure that all players under 20 years of age have >3 days rest before
202 their next match. The most common injuries were sprains and concussion, and these occurred more
203 commonly during matches than during training. Moreover, injuries most commonly occurred during
204 the third quarter of matches. Tackling was the action most likely to cause an injury. It might be advisable
205 to ensure that all players warm up properly and practise techniques that increase player concentration
206 before going back on the pitch after half-time. Insisting on training in good tackling technique might

207 also help reduce the number of injuries sustained. It would be interesting to extend this study to other
208 national teams to help confirm or refute the present results.

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Table 1: Incidence of injuries sustained by Spanish national U-18 and U-20 rugby team during over seasons 2015-2017 in training and matches

Team	Age, y Mean (SD)	Height, cm Mean (SD)	Body mass, kg Mean (SD)		Training	Match	Match according	
U-18	17.3(±0.5)	181(±7)	86.6(±11.7)	Players-hours	7470	192.5	< 3 Days between games	195
				Nº of injuries	8	19		27
				Incidence ^α	1.07 (0.32-1.81)	98.7 (56.5-140.8)		138.4 (89.9-186.9)
				Severity Days	11.0 (±4.0)	26.32 (±11.4)		30.4 (±8.4)
				Injury Burden ^β	12.5 (4.5-20.5)	2597.8 (1978.3-3217.2)		4209.2 [^] (3516.2-4902.1)
U-20	18.7(±0.5)	182(±6)	93.2(±16.2)	Players-hours	13170	320	≥ 3 Days between games	317.5
				Nº of injuries	16	35*		27
				Incidence ^α	1.21 (0.61-1.80)	109.3 (75.1-143.5)		85.0 (54.3-115.7)
				Severity Days	9.4 (±2.1)	26.8 (±6.7)		22.9 (±8.2)
				Injury Burden ^β	11.4 (5.6-17.1)	2931.2 (2432.5-3429.9)		1947.4 (1511.8-2382.9)
All	18.0(±0.9)	182(±6)	91.5(±14.9)	Nº of injuries	24	54*		
				Incidence ^α	1.16 (0.69-1.62)	105.3 (78.7-131.9)		
				Severity Days	9.96 (±1.9)	26.69 (±5.9)*		
				Injury Burden ^β	11.5 (6.9-16.2)	2812.2 (2422.9-3201.4)		

*: p<0,05. ^α: Injuries/1000 player-hours (95% CI). ^β: days absence/1000 player-hours (95% CI)

Table 2: Mean severity days-absence, number and proportion of injuries by grouped severity during training and matches

	Training	Match	All
Mean (95% CI)			
Severity days-absence	9.96(6.0-14.0)	26.6 (14.8-38.5)*	21.5 (13.1-29.9)
Number (%)			
Minimal (2-3)	7 (29.2%)	5(9.3%)	12 (15.4%)
Mild (4-7)	9 (37.5%)	18(33.3%)	27 (34.6%)
Moderate (8-28)	6 (25.0%)	19 (35.2%)	25 (32.1%)
Severe (>28)	2 (8.3%)	12 (22.2%)	14 (17.9%)
All	24 (100%)	54 (100%)	78(100%)

*: p<0,05; This is comparing training to match.

Table 3: Match and training injuries as a function of injury type

Injury type	Training	Match		All	
	n (%)	n (%)	Incidence ^α (95% CI)	Injury Burden ^β (95% CI)	n (%)
Concussion	2 (8.3%)	9 (16.7%)	17.5 (6.1-28.9)	268.6 (230.0-307.0)	11 (14.1%)
Dislocation/ subluxation	2 (8.3%)	1 (1.9%)	1.9 (0.01-5.7)	119.0 (90.9-147.0)	3 (3.8%)
Sprain/ ligament injury	6 (25.0%)	19 (35.2%)	37.0 (20.7-53.4)	1067.7 (800.3-1335.0)	25 (32.1%)
Fracture	2 (8.3%)	6 (11.1%)	11.7 (2.3-21.0)	575.6 (532.8-618.4)	8 (10.3%)
Other bone injuries	1 (4.2%)	0	0	0	1 (1.3%)
Lesion of meniscus, cartilage or discs	0	1 (1.9%)	1.9 (0.01-5.7)	417.5 (371.8-460.2)	1 (1.3%)
Muscle ruptura/tear/ strain/ cramps	5 (20.8%)	8 (14.7%)	15.6 (4.8-26.3)	240.3 (203.3-277.3)	13 (16.6%)
Tendon injury/ ruptura/ tendinopathy/ bursitis	5 (20.8%)	5 (9.2%)	9.7 (1.2-18.2)	44.8 (26.9-62.8)	10 (12.8%)
Haematoma/ contusion/ bruise	1 (4.2%)	5 (9.2%)	9.7 (1.2-18.2)	56.0 (36.1-76.0)	6 (7.6%)
All	24 (100%)	54 (100%)	105.3 (104.4-106.2)	2812.2 (2422.9-3201.4)	78 (100%)

α: Injuries/1000 player-hours (95% CI).β: days absence/1000 player-hours (95% CI)

Table 4: Match and training injuries as a function of injury location per injury type

	Injury tipe																		All n (%)
	Concussion		Dislocation/ subluxation		Sprain/ ligament injury		Fracture		Other bone injuries		Lesion of meniscus, cartilage or dics		Muscle ruptura/tear/ strain/ cramps		Tendon injury/ ruptura/ tendinopathy/ bursitis		Haematoma/ contusion/ bruise		
Injury location	Training	Match	Training	Match	Training	Match	Training	Match	Training	Match	Training	Match	Training	Match	Training	Match	Training	Match	
Head/ neck	2	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11(14.1%)
Neck/ cervical spine	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2(2.6%)
U-back/ sternum/ rib	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3(3.8%)
L-back	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1(1.3%)
Shoulder/ clavicle	0	0	1	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	10(12.8%)
Wrist	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3(3.8%)
Hand/ finger/ thumb	0	0	1	0	0	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7(9.0%)
Hip/ groin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	4(5.1%)
Anterior thigh	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	1	6(7.7%)
Posterior thigh	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	1	5(6.4%)
Knee	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	9(11.5%)
Lower leg/ achilles tendon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	3(3.8%)
Ankle	0	0	0	0	4	7	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	14(17.9%)
Foot/ toe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
																			78 (100%)

Table 5: Training camp and tournaments: weekly structure.

Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 8	Day 9	Day 10	Day 11	Day 12	Day 13	Day 14	Day 15	Day 16	Day 17
Training camp - European Men's under-20 championship																
<i>Training Camp</i>																
Arrival and Training	Training	Match	Training	Training	Match/Departure											
<i>European Men's under-20 championship</i>																
Arrival	Match	Training	Training	Match	Training	Training	Match	Departure								
Training camp - Men's under-20 Trophy																
<i>Training camp</i>																
Arrival and Training	Training	Training	Match	Training	Training	Training	Match/Departure									
<i>Men's U20 Trophy</i>																
Arrival	Training	Training	Training	Match	Training	Training	Training	Match	Training	Training	Training	Match	Training	Training	Training	Match

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